

Synthesis of Substituted *N*-(Benzyl/benzyloxy)glycine Ethyl Esters and Hydrazides

A. A. Munshi and J. P. Trivedi

Since reporting of the plant-growth regulating properties of maleic hydrazide¹, *N*-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)glycine² was found also to have herbicidal properties. Tuberculo-static tests were reported on *N*-(4-fluorophenyl) glycine, its ethyl ester, and hydrazide³. Recently, Finger *et al.*⁴ reported synthesis of *N*-phenylglycine ethyl ester and its hydrazides.

In order to evaluate tuberculo-static activities, several benzyl- and benzyloxy-glycine ethyl esters and the corresponding hydrazides have been reported in the present communication. The esters have been characterised by their *N*-acetyl derivatives and the hydrazides, by their sulphonamide derivatives.

p-Bromo- and *p*-chloro-benzyloxyanilines were prepared according to the procedure described by Boehme⁵ for synthesising benzyloxyanilines.

p-Bromobenzyloxyaniline: m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 4.92. C₁₃H₁₄ONBr requires N, 5.00%).

N-Acetyl derivative: m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 4.20. C₁₅H₁₄O₂NBr requires N, 4.46%).

p-Chlorobenzyloxyaniline: m.p. 102°. (Found: N, 5.58. C₁₃H₁₂ONCl requires N, 5.70%).

N-Acetyl derivative: m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 4.80. C₁₅H₁₄O₂NCl: requires N: 5.10%).

p-*n*-Butoxyaniline was prepared according to Gutekunst and Gray⁶.

The anilines were condensed with ethyl chloroacetate in presence of pyridine, when the glycines were obtained. These were characterised by preparing their *N*-acetyl derivatives. These glycines on treatment with hydrazine hydrate according to Buu-Hoi *et al.*³ and Baker *et al.*⁷ yielded the corresponding hydrazides. These were characterised by preparing their *p*-Tosyl derivatives, since the sulphonamides thus obtained could also be tested for their physiological activities.

1. Schoene and Hoffman, *Science*, 1940, 109, 580.

2. Veldstra and Boedig, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1940, 3, 278.

3. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 23, 180.

4. *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 405.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2502.

6. *Ibid.*, 1922, 44, 1742.

7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 307.

N-Benzyl- and *N*-benzyloxy-glycines are reported in Table I and their corresponding hydrazides in Table II.

TABLE I

No.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	M.P./B.P.	Formula,	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.
1	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	H	175°/60 mm	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N**	
2	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	-COMe	115°/742 mm	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	5.0 6.0
	"	H	230°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl	6.0 6.2
	"	-COMe	90°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	5.0 5.2
3	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	H	228°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr	4.8 5.1
	"	-COMe	111°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ NBr	4.3 4.5
4	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄	H	173°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ NCl	4.2 4.4
	"	-COMe	140°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCl	3.6 3.9
5	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄	H	180°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ NBr	3.7 3.9
	"	-COMe	154°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ NBr	3.3 3.5
6	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄	H	114°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N	4.8 4.9
	"	-COMe	136°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N	4.0 4.3
7	<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉ O.C ₆ H ₄	H	225°/760 mm	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	5.3 5.6
	"	-COMe	29°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	4.4 4.8

** Known compound.

TABLE II

No.	R.	M.P./B.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.
1	*	151°	C ₉ H ₁₃ ON ₃	N: 23.4% 23.5%
	<i>p</i> -Tosylamide	167°/760 mm	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	S: 9.5 9.6
2	*	91°	C ₉ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl	N: 19.3 19.7
	<i>p</i> -Tosylamide	228°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	S: 8.8 8.7
3	*	105°	C ₉ H ₁₂ ON ₃ Br	N: 16.2 16.3
	<i>p</i> -Tosylamide	233°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ BrS	S: 7.6 7.8
4	*	46°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	N: 12.6 13.6
	<i>p</i> -Tosylamide	108°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	S: 7.2 7.0
5	*	36°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Br	N: 12.0 12.0
	<i>p</i> -Tosylamide	44°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₃ BrS	S: 6.3 6.4
6	*	112°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	N: 15.2 15.5
	<i>p</i> -Tosylamide	123-25°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	S: 7.5 7.5
7	*	108-10°	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	N: 17.4 17.7
	<i>p</i> -Tosylamide	232°	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	S: 8.0 8.2

* The number corresponds to the same numbered compound in Table I.